

Navigating School Safety and Security: Teachers' Lived Experiences

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Abstract. This study explored teachers' lived experiences in navigating school safety and security measures in Gregorio Moralizon Elementary School-I, Manay North District, Davao Oriental Division. Specifically, it aimed to understand how teachers perceive and respond to current safety and security protocols, the challenges they face, and the coping strategies they employ. Using a phenomenological approach, the research captured in-depth insights through individual interviews and a focus group discussion. Data were analyzed using a thematic coding technique. For the first objective, which focused on teachers' experiences with current safety and security measures, key themes emerged, including Experiencing Enhanced Preparedness and Confidence During Emergencies, Improving Sense of Security Among Staff and Students, and Strengthening Collaboration and Awareness. However, participants also identified persistent challenges such as Facing Limited Resources and Infrastructure, and Increasing Workload and Stress. In response to these challenges, teachers employed various strategies. The second objective revealed themes of collaboration and communication, Professional development and training, and creating a positive school culture as effective coping mechanisms. From an educational management perspective, significant insights surfaced: Ensuring School Safety through Collaborative Leadership and Continuously Developing Professionally as a Key Strategy. These findings emphasize that school leaders and policymakers need to prioritize proactive and inclusive safety planning, provide adequate resources, and cultivate a supportive school culture to ensure staff well-being and student protection.

KEY WORDS

1. School Safety 2. Security Measures 3. Teacher Experiences

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1. Introduction

The wellness, teaching performance, and psychological health of teachers within educational workplaces is directly affected by safety and security issues. In recent years, there has been an increase in awareness of violence, bullying, intrusions, natural disasters, and many more. Teachers have to deal with a lot of responsibilities to do with prevention and response. This qualitative study looks at what teachers have to go through in terms of the effectiveness of safety measures and security protocols in the school setting. Hearing from these individuals, the study set out to cast light on these challenges and fears of school safety which in turn will help educators, policy makers, and school administrators understand the issues surrounding the decisions meant to make the school a more adaptive and safer learning environment.

One of the critical worldwide discrepancies regarding safety in schools is that security measures are applied heterogeneously across different schools. According to some studies, schools in poorer and rural areas are often short of resources which translates to minimal investment in security equipment, insufficiently trained security staff, and lack of proper training for teachers on handling emergencies (Graham et al., 2022). This inconsistency creates a disparity in teachers' experiences of safety, with some feeling more vulnerable due to a lack of effective preventive measures. Without proper and consistent safety practices, the potential for harm and security threats becomes more pronounced across different regions and types of schools. The growing concern about school safety not only affects physical security but also has psychological and emotional consequences for both students and teachers. Borum et al. (2019) claim that worry, stress, and poor academic performance can result from a persistent concern of possible threats such as school shootings, bullying, or violent occurrences. In spite of these glaring psychological impacts, a number of frameworks pertaining to school safety do not incorporate the psychological aspects of the students and the educators. Schools worldwide often lack sufficient counseling services, leaving those affected by safety concerns without adequate emotional support. This gap underscores the need for integrating mental health strategies into school safety policies. Another global gap is the limited involvement of teachers in designing safety and security policies. School safety protocols are often formulated by administrators and policymakers without adequately consulting the individuals who experience the risks firsthand, particularly students and teachers. As emphasized by Rigby and Smith (2021), involving these key stakeholders in the development of safety measures allows for more relevant, effective, and inclusive strategies that reflect the real concerns and experiences within the

school environment. This gap in participatory policy-making leads to the adoption of measures that may not fully address the nuanced needs of those most affected by safety risks. Natural calamities such as typhoons, earthquakes, and volcanic eruptions are common in The Philippines. Even so, numerous schools do not have adequate safety frameworks or complete disaster readiness strategies. A study by Cruz et al. (2020) although disaster risk reduction education is incorporated into the curriculum, safety drills and infrastructure development are not adequately implemented in practice. Schools often do not have adequate evacuation routes, emergency supplies, or disaster-trained personnel, leaving students and teachers vulnerable during natural disasters. This gap highlights the need for improved disaster readiness protocols across Philippine schools to ensure the safety of everyone during emergencies. Bullying, including cyberbullying, remains a significant issue in Philippine schools, affecting students' sense of safety and well-being. While the Anti-Bullying Act of 2013 was enacted to address this concern, its implementation varies, and many schools struggle to effectively manage and prevent bullying incidents. A Department of Education (DepEd) report claims that many students still endure bullying in spite of the current policies, which can result in anxiety, despair, and sub-par academic performance (DepEd, 2019). This gap in enforcing anti-bullying measures indicates a need for better monitoring and stronger intervention programs in schools to ensure students feel safe from harassment both online and in person. Having no surveillance cameras, alarms, or trained guards constitute an important gap in the safety and security features in Philippine schools. Many security systems are devoid in public schools, especially in schools situated in rural or underprivileged areas, because of budgetary limitations. A study by David and Santiago (2021) found that public schools in urban centers are more likely to have

security infrastructure, while rural schools remain highly vulnerable to break-ins, theft, and other security threats. This uneven distribution of resources presents a serious concern for the safety of students and teachers, highlighting the need for equitable funding and prioritization of school security measures across all regions. A critical current issue impacting the safety and security of schools in our region is the insufficient provision of mental health support for students. Although there is a pressing need to integrate mental health support in educational institutions as per the 2018 Mental Health Act, most of these schools continue to be haunted by resource gaps, a lack of trained professionals, and minimal awareness. This challenge is particularly evident in Gregorio Moralizon Elementary School- I in the Manay North District,

where teachers are at the forefront of addressing students' safety concerns despite the lack of accessible psychological support. As they navigate issues such as bullying, anxiety, and trauma within the school environment, teachers are often left to manage these challenges with minimal guidance or resources. Existing research has largely focused on policy implementation and student well-being, but little attention has been given to teachers' lived experiences in ensuring school safety and security. This study sought to uncover the multidimensional realities they contend with – the strategies they employ, their prevailing challenges, and gaps that require urgent attention to refine the existent systemic structures for a safer educational milieu – by probing into their perspectives.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aims to explore and understand the experiences and perspectives of teachers regarding school safety and security measures. By examining their narratives, the study seeks to uncover the specific challenges, concerns, and perceptions that influence their sense of safety within the school environment. It aims to identify the strengths and weaknesses of current safety protocols, offering insights into how schools can improve their security practices. Ultimately, the objective of this study is to propose recommendations that aid in the development of an educational environment which is safe and conducive for learning for both teachers and students.

1.2. Research Questions—The purpose of this qualitative phenomenological study was to explore and understand the lived experiences and perceptions of teachers regarding safety and security measures within their school environment. Specifically, this research provided answers to the following:

- (1) What are the experiences of the teachers in the current safety and security measures in the school?
- (2) How do the teachers overcome the challenges in the implementation of safety and security measures in the school?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the experiences of the participants?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following definitions shall be used throughout the study.

School Safety

This refers to the measures, policies, and practices in place to protect students and staff from physical, emotional, and psychological

harm within the school environment. In this study, school safety is explored through teachers' lived experiences in handling issues such as bullying, mental health concerns, and emergency preparedness.

School Security

This pertains to the structures and protocols designed to prevent threats, control access, and ensure a secure learning environment. In the context of this study, school security includes teachers' experiences with enforcing safety measures, responding to security concerns, and managing risks within the school setting.

1.4. Significant of the Study—This study provided valuable insights into the lived experiences of teachers as they manage and respond to these challenges. By understanding their perspectives, this research contributed to existing discussions on school safety and security, highlighting areas that required policy improvements, enhanced support systems, and more effective interventions. The results of this study could be useful for formulating strategies that foster a safe and supportive educational climate for all relevant constituents. Specifically, this study is beneficial to the following:

Students

Helps students concentrate on their academic and personal development without fear or interruptions by fostering a safer and more secure learning environment.

Teachers

The study provides insights into challenges and strategies for maintaining school safety, enabling teachers to feel more supported and effective in their roles.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—According to Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1943), which Taormina and Gao (2023) updated, safety is a basic human need that must be satisfied before higher-order functions like learning and self-actualization can take place. In the context of school safety and security, teachers believe that these elements are crucial for students'

Teachers' Narratives

This refers to the personal accounts and lived experiences shared by teachers regarding their role in maintaining school safety and security. In this study, teachers' narratives provide firsthand insights into the challenges, strategies, and realities they face in fostering a secure and supportive learning environment.

School Heads

The findings offer school heads actionable recommendations to strengthen safety policies and foster a culture of security and trust within their institutions.

Department of Education Officials

The study provides valuable data to inform policymaking, ensuring that safety measures in schools align with the needs and experiences of educators and learners.

Stakeholders

It encourages collaboration among stakeholders, such as parents, community members, and private organizations, in creating and sustaining safe and secure educational spaces.

Future Researchers

Future researchers can build upon this study in order to gain a better understanding of the subject. In addition, this work may encourage other readers to examine the realities faced by Indigenous learners. Additionally, this study may inspire further research which sheds light on these individuals' circumstances in their home life and work life.

academic success and emotional well-being because their experiences demonstrate how unsafe environments, whether brought on by bullying, violence, or insufficient policies, impede student learning. Similarly, the research is also tied to Social Safety Theory (Porges, 2019) which claims that people function best where they feel socially and physically safe and

teachers' concerns about the impact of school safety issues on the students' psyche reflect the lack of basic security measures or functional policies in place resulting in heightened anxiety, disengagement, and low performance, and the teachers' efforts to mitigate these psychosocial factors only further accentuate the social vulnerability and therefore amplify the social safety role of educators within a trusting bond. Additionally, the study can be understood through the Routine Activity Theory (Cohen Felson, 1979), which was later developed by Pratt and Turanovic (2019). According to this theory, crime happens when three factors come together: a motivated offender, a suitable target, and the lack of capable guardianship. In school settings, teachers act as "guardians" who deter potential threats by using coping mechanisms like enforcing rules, keeping an eye on student behavior, and coordinating with security personnel. These measures reduce risks and enhance safety outcomes. Furthermore, the study can be analyzed through the scope of Broken Windows Theory (Wilson Kelling, 1982), which Keizer, Lindenberg and Steg (2019) revisited for suggesting that maintaining order by dealing with minor transgressions, such as vandalism, can avert greater security risks. Teachers' reflections emphasize the necessity of taking preemptive action through the enforcement of school rules and prompt attention to even the smallest of minor behaviors. Figure 1 highlights two key research questions related to school safety and security: What are the experiences of the teachers in the current safety and security

measures in the school? and how do teachers overcome the challenges in the implementation of safety and security measures in the school? The overlap between these questions emphasizes the importance of understanding shared experiences and insights from participants to create a holistic view of school safety issues. By focusing on both the perception of safety measures and the specific challenges encountered, the diagram suggests that insights drawn from teachers can offer valuable perspectives for improving security protocols. The left circle represents the first research question, which centers on the experiences of the teachers in the current safety and security measures in the school. This aspect of the research is essential because individual perceptions shape how secure these groups feel in their learning environment. Their perceptions can highlight gaps between the intended protection and their lived experiences of security. On the right side, the second circle addresses the specific safety concerns and challenges that teachers' face within the school environment. This might include issues like bullying, physical threats, or inadequate crisis management procedures. By identifying these specific challenges, the research can pinpoint areas where current safety protocols may be failing or lacking altogether. The overlapping section in the middle illustrates that both perspectives of safety measures and specific challenges faced—are essential for gaining a complete understanding of the safety landscape within schools.

2. Methodology

This chapter described the approach taken in conducting the study as well as in data collection. Additionally, it covered research design, philosophical assumptions, research subjects and sampling, data collection methods, research tools used, study trustworthiness, and ethical issues. The most frequently utilized qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was quite useful in obtaining a certain type of data. Participant observation was suitable for gathering information about behaviors that happen in everyday life

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

settings. In-depth interviews (IDI) were the most effective for data collection concerning an individual’s private life, sensitive topics, attitudes, and experiences. Focus groups were useful for obtaining information on group cultural norms and for providing general summaries of many group issues of concern for a cultural group/subgroup. Phenomenology, according to Patton (2019), is an investigation that asks, “What is the structure and essence of the experience of this phenomenon for these people?” This description was a good fit for the research’s objective, which was to compare how the new normal was implemented back then and now in order to better understand the experiences of school heads. Giorgi (2007) suggested scholars to expect a more thorough and comprehensive examination than the provided description suggested. Information is just the top of the iceberg, he suggested.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption served as a foundational framework for collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data on school safety and security as perceived by teachers. It provided the necessary background for drawing conclusions and making informed decisions regarding safety protocols and their implementation. In this study, philosophical assumptions guided the exploration of teachers’ lived experiences and coping strategies in maintaining a secure school environment. A well-structured research study begins with the careful selection of a topic, research problem, and paradigm. In this case, the focus on school safety and security required an appropriate paradigm to frame the investigation. Stanage (2019) traced the concept of ‘paradigm’ back to its Greek (paradeigma) and Latin (paradigma) origins, meaning pattern, model, or example. A paradigm shapes a researcher’s way of thinking, serving as a guiding model for inquiry and decision-making. In the context of this study, the selected paradigm influenced how teachers’ experiences with school safety measures were examined and interpreted. According to Denzin and Lincoln (2020), a research paradigm is a “basic set of beliefs that guide action.” This viewpoint is consistent with their description. It involves the “ultimate” or fundamental concepts that influence

the researcher's methodological decisions and worldview. The paradigm that was selected for this study assisted in framing the teachers' stories and made sure that their perspectives on security issues, safety regulations, and coping strategies were methodically examined. The goal of the study was to produce significant contributions to educational administration and policy development concerning school safety and security by firmly establishing the research on a philosophical premise.

Ontology

In this study, I explored the lived experiences of teachers regarding the implementation of school safety and security measures. Their narratives provided insight into how they perceived, navigated, and coped with safety challenges within their schools. I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants, ensuring their perspectives were authentically represented through extensive quotes and thematic analysis. Their responses were systematically coded and analyzed to identify both commonalities and unique viewpoints regarding school safety issues. To maintain the integrity of the research, I carefully coded responses to ensure reliability and consistency in the analysis. Every effort was made to uphold the authenticity of the participants' narratives, avoiding personal bias throughout the study. By presenting the teachers' experiences accurately, this research aimed to contribute valuable insights into the effectiveness of current safety measures and the coping strategies employed in maintaining a secure learning environment.

Epistemology

For this study, I employed a phenomenological approach with thematic analysis, as recommended by Davidson (2020) and Jones (2021). This approach was chosen because it aligns with the goal of understanding the lived experiences of teachers regarding school safety and security. As an active researcher, I engaged closely with the participants, ensuring that their per-

spectives and insights were authentically captured. Through direct interactions, I gathered valuable information on how teachers perceived and implemented safety measures, as well as the coping strategies they employed to navigate security challenges within their schools. By maintaining an immersive research approach, I ensured that the study provided a deep and meaningful exploration of the participants' experiences. This close engagement allowed for a more nuanced understanding of how teachers adapted to and addressed school safety concerns, ultimately contributing to a richer interpretation of their narratives.

Axiology

In this study, I upheld the dignity and value of every detail provided by the teachers regarding their experiences with school safety and security. Given the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered, I remained mindful of the ethical responsibility to respect and accurately represent their perspectives. The responses of the participants were carefully interpreted, ensuring that their insights on safety measures, security challenges, and coping strategies were presented with integrity. By recognizing the influence of values on the research process, I aimed to present a balanced and authentic portrayal of the teachers' lived experiences. This approach ensured that the study not only captured objective findings but also reflected the meaningful, subjective realities that shaped school safety and security from the perspective of educators.

Rhetoric

By employing a narrative approach, I was able to convey the lived experiences of the ten (10) teacher-participants from Gregorio Morazon Elementary School-I, Manay North District, Davao Oriental Division, each with at least five (5) years of teaching experience. This ensured that their voices were authentically represented in the study. This approach allowed for a deeper, more personal exploration of their

coping strategies, challenges, and perceptions regarding school security. Writing in the first person also reinforced my active role in the research process, ensuring that the study remained

grounded in the voices of the participants while maintaining clarity and coherence in presenting their insights.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—In this study, I rely on qualitative assumptions to shape the research process, from data collection to interpretation. Since my focus is on exploring the lived experiences of teachers in implementing school safety and security measures, a qualitative approach allows me to gain a deeper understanding of their perspectives, emotions, and coping strategies. I acknowledge that reality is subjective and constructed through personal experiences, making it essential to capture rich, descriptive narratives from my participants. By embracing qualitative assumptions, I prioritize an in-depth exploration of teachers' insights rather than relying on numerical data or generalized conclusions. Using open-ended inquiry, I ensure that the voices of my participants are authentically represented, providing a more comprehensive picture of the challenges, strategies, and implications surrounding school safety. Additionally, I establish close interaction with my participants, allowing for a more meaningful interpretation of their experiences.

Ultimately, the qualitative assumptions in this study guide how I gather, analyze, and present data, ensuring that my findings remain rooted in the realities of those who navigate school safety challenges firsthand. Through this approach, I aim to contribute valuable insights that can inform policies, enhance security measures, and support educators in creating safer learning environments.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study employed a qualitative phenomenological research design to explore the lived experiences of teachers in implementing school safety and security measures. Through this approach, I sought to understand how teachers perceive, experience, and respond to various safety challenges in their schools. By capturing their personal narratives, I aimed to uncover patterns, themes, and coping strategies that highlight their crucial role in ensuring a secure learning environment. This study focused on the depth and complexity of their experiences, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the realities of school safety from their perspectives.

2.4. Ethical Considerations—This section outlines the ethical principles that will guide this research, ensuring the protection and well-being of the participating teacher-respondents. These principles include a commitment to social value, informed consent, addressing the vulnerability of research respondents, upholding privacy and confidentiality, carefully considering risks, benefits, and safety, ensuring justice, maintaining transparency, acknowledging my qualifications as the researcher, addressing potential conflicts of interest, ensuring the adequacy of resources,

and recognizing community relevance.

Social Value

I recognized the significant social value inherent in this research. By focusing on the lived experiences of teachers in navigating school safety and security at Gregorio Morализон Elementary School-I, I contributed to a deeper understanding of the challenges and strategies employed at the school level to ensure a safe learning environment. This aligns with my commitment to conducting research that yields tangible benefits for the teachers themselves, the stu-

dents, the school administration, and the wider community in Manay North District. I believe that the findings from this study could inform school safety protocols, professional development initiatives, and policy recommendations aimed at enhancing the security and well-being of the entire school community.

Informed Consent

I placed a strong emphasis on obtaining informed consent from each participating teacher. Before they participated in any interviews or other data collection methods, I personally ensured that they received clear and comprehensive explanation of my study's purpose, the specific procedures involved, the estimated time commitment for their participation, and their absolute right to withdraw at any point without any negative consequences. I provided a detailed consent form outlining these aspects, and I only proceeded with their participation once I am confident, they fully understood and voluntarily agreed to get involved.

Vulnerability of Research Respondents

I acknowledged that teachers, due to their professional roles and potential concerns about their standing within the school, may be vulnerable when discussing sensitive topics related to school safety and security. They might hesitate to share their honest opinions or experiences due to fear of repercussions or judgment. Recognizing this potential vulnerability, I was committed to creating a research environment built on trust and openness. I explicitly assured participants that their involvement is entirely voluntary and that their individual responses would be kept strictly confidential and anonymous in any reporting. My aim was to empower them to share their experiences freely, knowing their input would be valued and would not negatively impact their careers or their relationship with the school administration.

Privacy and Confidentiality

I prioritized the privacy and confidentiality of all participating teachers. I understood

the sensitive nature of discussions surrounding school safety and security, and the importance of creating a safe space for teachers to share their insights. To ensure this, I implemented robust measures to protect their identities and responses. Each participant was assigned a unique code, and all collected data, including interview transcripts and field notes, were stored securely with access limited solely to me. In any dissemination of my findings, I presented the data in an aggregated form, ensuring that no individual teacher or their specific experiences could be identified.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety

I have carefully considered the potential risks to participating teachers, which I anticipated to be minimal, primarily involving the time they dedicated to the study and perhaps some emotional reflection on potentially challenging or concerning incidents related to school safety. However, I believed the benefits of their participation significantly outweighed these concerns. By sharing their lived experiences, they contributed to a valuable body of knowledge that can inform improvements in school safety protocols and support systems for teachers and students. I ensured that all data collection activities were conducted respectfully of their time and professional obligations, prioritizing their comfort and well-being throughout the process. I was also mindful of the potential for sensitive information to arise and was prepared to offer resources or support needed.

Justice

I was committed to ensuring justice in this research by including a diverse group of teachers from Gregorio Moralizon Elementary School-I with varying levels of experience and perspectives on school safety and security. This approach ensured that a range of voices and experiences are represented in the study. Furthermore, I ensured that any relevant findings from the study were shared with the participating teachers and the school administration in

Manay North District, providing them with potential insights that could inform local school safety practices and policies. My goal was to ensure that the knowledge gained from their experiences can contribute to a safer and more secure environment for all members of the school community.

Transparency

I understand that transparency is crucial for building trust and fostering open communication. Throughout the research process, I maintained clear and open lines of communication with the participating teachers. I ensured that they were well-informed about the study's objectives, my methodologies, and the potential impact of their contributions on understanding and improving school safety and security. I was also readily available to address any questions or concerns they may have, fostering a collaborative and respectful research environment.

Qualification of the Researcher

As the researcher undertaking this thesis, I brought a strong foundation of relevant qualifications that were essential for conducting ethical and impactful research. I possessed a comprehensive understanding of the Philippine educational system and the critical importance of school safety and security. My skills in qualitative research methodologies, particularly narrative inquiry and in-depth interviews, equipped me to design a rigorous and insightful study that captured the lived experiences of teachers. Furthermore, my commitment to ethical research practices and my understanding of the challenges faced by educators in ensuring a safe learning environment allowed me to approach this research with sensitivity and respect. By being transparent about my qualifications and my commitment to ethical conduct, I reassured the participants that this study was conducted with integrity and with their well-being in mind.

Conflict of Interest

I was vigilant in identifying and addressing any potential conflicts of interest that might

arise from my connections with Gregorio Moralizon Elementary School-I or the participating teachers. Should any such conflicts, perceived or actual, emerge, I could have disclosed them transparently and have taken steps to ensure they do not compromise the integrity and objectivity of my research on teachers' experiences navigating school safety and security. My priority was to conduct unbiased and trustworthy research that accurately reflects the realities faced by the teachers.

Adequacy of Facilities

I was committed to providing the necessary resources and support to facilitate the teachers' participation in the study. This includes ensuring comfortable and private spaces for the interviews or data collection activities within Gregorio Moralizon Elementary School-I and suitable alternative location in Manay. I also ensured that the process was conducted in a way that minimized disruption to their teaching schedules and professional responsibilities. By prioritizing the adequacy of facilities, I created a supportive and respectful environment that encouraged open and honest sharing from the teachers. This approach not only enhanced the quality of the data collected but also reflected my ethical responsibility to respect the participants' time and well-being.

Community Relevance

I believe this research holds significant relevance for the educational community in Manay, Davao Oriental, particularly for the teachers, students, and administrators at Gregorio Moralizon Elementary School-I and other schools in the Manay North District. Insights gained into teachers' lived experiences in navigating school safety and security informed local school safety protocols, training programs for educators, and collaborative efforts with the wider community to create safer learning environments. By focusing on the teachers' perspectives, my research contributed to a more comprehensive understanding of school safety challenges and effective

tive strategies, ultimately benefiting the entire school community in Manay.

2.5. Research Participants—In selecting the research participants for this study, I employed a purposive sampling design, ensuring that individuals were chosen based on specific criteria relevant to the investigation. This method, also known as judgmental or selective sampling, allowed me to deliberately identify participants whose experiences provided meaningful insights into the implementation of school safety and security measures. Since purposive sampling relied on the researcher's judgment to obtain a representative sample, it was an effective approach in capturing the perspec-

tives of teachers who have firsthand experienced maintaining school safety. For this study, I selected ten (10) teachers from Gregorio Moralizon Elementary School-I, Manay North District, Davao Oriental Division, all of whom had at least five (5) years of teaching experience. These participants were engaged in in-depth interviews to share their narratives on school safety and security. To maintain confidentiality, coding was used to protect their identities, with each participant being assigned identifiers ranging from IDI-FT1 to IDI-FT10. This approach ensured the authenticity of the findings while safeguarding the privacy of the participants.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—In this study, I played various roles to attain the success of the study. First, I asked for permission to conduct the study which started from the Schools Division Superintendent, and then to the participants of my study. I recorded the actual interview to achieve the needs of this type of research. The interview's goal is to gain a deeper understanding of the experiences of the learners in the

new normal way of teaching and learning. The interview include how the Department of Education should improve its programs. After the needed data has been gathered, everything has been transcribed and analyzed by the researcher. According to Greenbank (2019) if the quality of this research has to deal with biases and assumptions in dealing with the people involved in the research, human instruments are more crucial to study.

2.7. Data Collection—According to Creswell (2019), an important step in the research process is selecting the study site and participants while ensuring access and rapport to obtain meaningful data. Purposeful sampling must be planned, and appropriate data collection methods must be determined. Researchers must also anticipate potential field issues, such as insufficient data, premature withdrawal from the site, or data loss. Furthermore, data must be stored securely for easy retrieval and protection. In this study, I followed a structured data-gathering process. On May 5, 2025, I sent a formal request to the Schools Division

Superintendent of Davao Oriental to conduct the study at Gregorio Moralizon Elementary School-I. The request included a cover letter, an explanation of the study's objectives, participant selection criteria, and copies of Chapters 1 and 2, along with the research instrument. I commenced data collection only after receiving official approval. On May 9, 2025, I received the approval from the SDS. On the same day, I submitted a formal letter to the school head of Gregorio Moralizon Elementary School-I. This letter detailed the study's purpose, research procedures, and the participation of selected teachers. Approval from the school head was ob-

tained on the same day. On May 10, 2025 I met with the selected teacher-participants to provide an orientation about the study and secure their informed consent. Participants were assured of confidentiality, voluntary participation, and their right to withdraw at any stage. On May 12, 2025, I conducted in-depth interviews with the 10 teacher-participants. Each session followed a semi-structured interview guide, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder to ensure accuracy. Participants' demographic profiles were also documented. During interviews, I actively listened, took notes, and sought clarifications when necessary. On May 13, 2025, I transcribed the interviews verbatim. Since participants primarily responded in their vernacular language, I carefully translated their responses into English while ensuring the integrity of their statements. On May 14, 2025, I systematically coded the transcriptions and categorized data

into emerging themes. This process allowed me to identify patterns in the responses and establish connections among participants' experiences. On May 15, 2025, I conducted a follow-up Focus Group Discussion (FGD) with the same participants. This session served to validate the findings, clarify responses requiring further justification, and gather additional insights. The new data collected was integrated into the existing themes and analyzed accordingly. On May 16, 2025, I refined the thematic analysis, ensuring coherence in the identified themes and patterns. By this time, all necessary adjustments and validations were completed, leading to the comprehensive interpretation of findings. This structured timeline ensured that data collection and analysis were conducted efficiently and within the planned schedule, maintaining the integrity and credibility of the study.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, I carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed all the data collected. I began by reflecting on my own experiences related to school safety and security to acknowledge any potential biases and set them aside, ensuring that the focus remained on the perspectives of the teacher-participants from Gregorio Moralizon Elementary School-I. To analyze the data, I first identified significant statements from the participants' narratives, giving equal importance to each response. I then filtered out repetitive and overlapping statements to refine the data into meaningful categories. These significant statements were grouped into broader themes, forming "meaningful units" that encapsulated common experiences and perceptions regarding school safety and security. Following this, I crafted a descriptive

account of "what" the participants experienced in relation to school safety measures, highlighting their insights on challenges, coping strategies, and best practices. I then developed a structural description, illustrating "how" these experiences occurred within the specific context of their school environment. This step involved examining factors such as the school's policies, resources, and external influences that shaped their experiences. Finally, I integrated both the textural and structural descriptions to construct a composite narrative that captured the essence of the participants' lived experiences. This final interpretation provided a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon, ensuring that the study remained grounded in the authentic voices of the teacher-participants while maintaining the rigor of phenomenological research.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The analytical framework for this study was designed to

be flexible, allowing for data collection and analysis to occur either sequentially or simul-

taneously. The gathered data was carefully examined, organized, and categorized according to key themes and topics. To ensure a structured and in-depth analysis of the teachers' narratives on school safety and security, I utilized Colaizzi's seven-step method. The first step involved thoroughly reading and re-reading the transcribed interviews of the teacher-participants from Gregorio Moralizon Elementary School-I. This immersion process allowed me to fully grasp the context and depth of their experiences, ensuring that their perspectives were accurately understood. Through repeated engagement with the data, I was able to recognize emerging patterns and subtle nuances. Next, I identified significant statements within the transcripts—phrases or sentences that directly reflected the teachers' lived experiences regarding school safety and security. These statements were carefully extracted to maintain the integrity of their insights. In the third step, I formulated meanings from the extracted statements by interpreting their underlying significance. This process involved categorizing the statements into broader themes that encapsulated the key aspects of the teachers' experiences, providing a clearer structure for the analysis. Following this, I systematically applied the first three steps to each interview, ensuring that

every narrative was examined with equal depth. By analyzing each participant's account individually and then comparing them across all participants, I was able to identify common themes, recurring patterns, and unique variations in their perspectives. Once the key themes were established, I developed an exhaustive description of the findings, ensuring that all insights from the data were systematically documented. This comprehensive account maintained the authenticity of the participants' voices while presenting the analysis in a structured and coherent manner. In the sixth step, I synthesized the exhaustive description to establish the fundamental structure of the phenomenon. By refining the themes, I was able to construct a clear and insightful portrayal of the teachers' lived experiences in ensuring school safety and security. Finally, to validate the findings, I engaged in discussions with experts and independent reviewers to confirm the accuracy and credibility of the analysis. Their feedback helped strengthen the study by ensuring that the interpretations remained faithful to the participants' narratives. By employing Colaizzi's method, this study provided a rigorous and systematic analysis of the qualitative data while preserving the authenticity and depth of the teacher-participants' experiences.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Ensuring trustworthiness was necessary to successfully tackle credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. Given that this was a qualitative study, how the research process was conducted impacted its accuracy, fundamentally influencing the validity of the outcomes. Trustworthiness was critical in judging the value of this study, which ensured that the contribution made to comprehension of school safety and security from teachers at Gregorio Moralizon Elementary School-I was credible and valuable. In measuring school safety and security, quali-

tative studies focused on a different set of constructs – trustworthiness, which was the equivalent of reliability and validity bundled together. This study, by Harts (2019) maintained trustworthiness using four key components which guides the framework of the study.

Credibility

Was established by conducting in-depth interviews with teachers until data saturation was reached. By gathering comprehensive narratives, I ensured that the study accurately reflected the real-life experiences of teachers regarding school safety and security. Prolonged

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study as cited by (Finlayson et al. 2018)

engagement with the participants also strengthened credibility, as it allowed for a deeper understanding of their perspectives.

Transferability

Was answered by the detailed accounts of the context, participants, and setting of the study. Though qualitative research does not aim for generalizability like quantitative research, I made sure that my readers would be able to judge whether the results could be relevant to other similar situations. Other schools with comparable challenges with safety and security were provided with context rich enough for valuable comparisons.

Confirmability

Was accomplished through the reduction of researcher bias and from relying exclusively on the teachers' accounts for drawing conclusions. In order to remain objective, I incorporated the exact words of the participants and kept an audit trail of the entire research process,

encompassing interviews, field notes, and thematic analyses. This process guaranteed that the participants' experiences were accurately represented instead of my subjective interpretations dominating the findings.

Dependability

Was ensured through a transparent and well-documented research process. The participants were given opportunities to review and verify the accuracy of their interview transcripts and the study's findings. Their feedback was incorporated to maintain the integrity of the data. Additionally, peer reviews and consultations with research experts helped refine the analysis and interpretations. By adhering to these principles of trustworthiness, this study maintained high ethical and methodological standards, ensuring that the findings provided a meaningful and reliable insight into the safety and security experiences of teachers at Gregorio Moralizon Elementary School-I.

3. Results and Discussion

This study section addresses the research questions and their related answers based on the participants' feedback. The investigation explored teachers' experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights as they navigate the blended learning of scientific concepts.

3.1. *Experiences of the Teachers in The Current School Safety and Security Measures*

—The protection of the school personnel and students is one of the major priorities of any academic institution. Over the past few years, heightened concerns over violence, health crises, bullying, and even natural catastrophes have forced schools to adopt even stricter sets of safety policies and security protocols. These measures include the installation of surveillance systems, regular emergency drills, visitor management systems, and strict health protocols. While these strategies are meant to foster a secure learning environment, the actual experiences of teachers, who are at the frontline of enforcing and living through these protocols, are often underexplored. The involvement of teachers in preserving order within a school is very helpful. Their perceptions, challenges, and coping mechanisms provide valuable insight

3.1.1. *Experiencing Enhanced Preparedness and Confidence During Emergencies*

—Teachers feel more confident and prepared to handle emergencies such as earthquakes, fire drills, and lockdowns due to regular training and established safety protocols. In today's educational environment, ensuring the safety and security of all school stakeholders has become a top priority. Teachers, as frontliners in the school system, are directly involved in implementing and monitoring various safety protocols, from conducting emergency drills to managing classroom discipline in alignment with security policies. Their daily experiences provide valuable insight into how effective these measures are and how they influence the overall

into the effectiveness and practicality of current safety measures. Understanding their experiences helps school administrators and policymakers enhance the implementation of safety policies while ensuring the physical and psychological well-being of the teaching workforce. This study aims to explore the teachers' lived experiences concerning the present safety and security measures in schools, highlighting both the successes and the challenges they encounter. Since they are directly in charge of assisting students in times of emergency and encouraging a preparation culture, teachers play a crucial role in the effective execution of school safety programs, according to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2021). However, how well-prepared and supported the instructors feel in doing their duties which varies based on institutional support, training, and accessible resources is a critical factor in the success of these programs.

teaching and learning atmosphere. Exploring these experiences can help identify best practices, strengths, and areas that require further improvement in school safety initiatives. Teachers' experiences in enforcing safety and security protocols often reflect both progress and challenges within school systems. As highlighted by Astor, Benbenishty, and Estrada (2019), the perceptions and active participation of teachers significantly influence the effectiveness of school safety initiatives, particularly when they are supported with adequate training and institutional backing. Without such support, even well-designed safety measures may fail to meet their intended outcomes, placing both educators and learners at risk. Teachers' growing confidence

in handling emergency situations reflects the positive impact of consistent safety training and preparedness drills in schools. Initially, many educators feel anxious and uncertain when faced with drills such as earthquake or fire simulations. However, through regular orientation and practice facilitated by the school, they gradually develop a stronger sense of preparedness. This transition from fear to confidence is crucial, as teachers are responsible for guiding and protecting students during emergencies. Their familiarity with safety protocols—such as evacuation routes, headcounts, and response procedures—ensures a smoother, more organized response that prioritizes the welfare of everyone involved. Moreover, the active support and clear communication from school administrators contribute significantly to this improved prepared-

3.1.2. Improving Sense of Security Among Staff and Students —The presence of visible safety features, such as security guards, stricter access control, contributes to a safer school environment, making both teachers and students feel more protected. The systematic and overt application of safety precautions within the school environment have greatly enhanced the perception of safety among the employees and learners alike. The presence security personnel at entry points, identification badges, and visitor log-books has created an environment where school members feel protected from external threats and unauthorized access. Teachers have expressed that these measures not only deter potential incidents but also provide peace of mind during school hours. When students observe that their teachers feel secure, it promotes a classroom environment that is conducive to learning and emotional well-being. In addition, this heightened sense of security has allowed teachers to focus more on instruction rather than constantly worrying about safety concerns. Knowing that the school has taken concrete steps to ensure their protection, educators feel more val-

ued and supported by the administration. This perception of safety strengthens trust between the teaching staff and school leadership, encouraging greater cooperation and commitment. As a result, both students and teachers experience reduced anxiety, increased attendance, and a stronger sense of belonging within the school community. According to Bosworth, Ford, and Hernández (2021), a safe school environment has a direct impact on the academic achievement and emotional health of both instructors and children. People in the school community are more likely to feel emotionally and physically supported when safety procedures are in place and regularly followed, which improves the school atmosphere. Moreover, the interview reveals that these safety efforts foster a sense of trust between teachers and school administrators. When school leaders demonstrate a clear commitment to the safety and well-being of the school community—through regular updates, safety drills, and transparent policies—teachers feel more valued and respected. This trust enhances collaboration, boosts morale, and contributes to a more stable and positive school

climate where both educators and learners can thrive. The interview underscores how visible and consistent safety measures, such as security guards, and strict visitor protocols, play a crucial role in enhancing teachers' sense of security within the school environment. These measures provide teachers with a sense of reassurance, allowing them to focus more on their educational responsibilities rather than being distracted by concerns over potential threats. Moreover, this heightened security not only benefits the teachers but also positively impacts the students, who feel more at ease and are less anxious during drills or unexpected incidents. Teachers, in turn, model calmness and confidence, further rein-

3.1.3. Strengthening Collaboration and Awareness—Safety drills and planning have fostered a culture of teamwork among teachers and staff. There is increased awareness and shared responsibility in implementing safety practices across the school. The implementation of safety drills and planning has led to stronger collaboration and a shared sense of responsibility among teachers and school staff. When safety measures are prioritized, it requires active participation from everyone involved, ensuring that no one is left out of the safety protocols. Teachers collaborate with school administrators, security personnel, and other staff members to establish clear roles and responsibilities during drills and actual emergencies. This collective approach helps build a more organized and coordinated response, ensuring that all areas of the school are covered and that every individual knows their role when an emergency arises. Moreover, these safety drills have significantly raised awareness among school staff about the importance of being proactive in preventing accidents and handling crises. Teachers are more attuned to their surroundings and are often the first to identify and report potential hazards. This heightened awareness ensures that teachers are not only prepared for emergencies but also proactive in en-

forcing a safe and supportive atmosphere that fosters better learning and emotional well-being for both students and staff. This creates an environment where safety is prioritized, contributing to a more positive and productive school experience. A secure and encouraging learning environment has a big impact on student performance and teacher retention, claim Osher, Berg, and Malecki (2019). Teachers are more likely to form close bonds with one another, exhibit higher levels of instructional competence, and stay dedicated to their jobs when they believe their school is a safe place to be both physically and emotionally.

Ensuring safety measures are maintained throughout the school day. As a result, the school becomes a safer and more efficient place for both students and staff, as everyone is actively engaged in creating and maintaining a secure environment. According to Johnson and Lee (2019), effective school safety programs thrive on collaboration, where the active involvement of teachers, staff, and administrators is crucial for creating a shared understanding of safety protocols. This collaboration not only enhances emergency preparedness but also strengthens the overall school culture by fostering trust, open communication, and a unified commitment to the well-being of all school members. The increased collaboration among school staff has been one of the most noticeable outcomes of implementing safety drills and planning. Before these practices were regularly established, teachers were primarily focused on their individual roles and responsibilities. However, safety drills have fostered a collective sense of duty, with everyone involved teachers, administrators, security personnel, and support staff working together as a cohesive team. This shift has led to more open communication, clearer understanding of roles during emergencies, and a stronger sense of shared responsibility for the

safety of students and staff. Through these efforts, staff members are not just concerned with their own specific tasks but are also aware of how their actions impact the overall safety and well-being of the school community. Furthermore, the emphasis on collaboration has also heightened staff awareness and understanding of the safety protocols in place. As teachers, security personnel, and administrators actively participate in safety drills, they become more attuned to their surroundings and the safety measures that need to be consistently followed. This heightened awareness is not limited to drills but has translated into daily practices. Teachers are now more likely to identify and report potential hazards in and around the school, ensuring that issues are addressed promptly. The proactive approach allows the school to address concerns before they escalate into emergencies, leading to a safer school environment overall. The school's administration has played a crucial role in facilitating this culture of collaboration by being transparent and open to input from the staff. By clearly communicating the safety protocols and showing a commitment to safety, the administration has earned the trust of the teachers and staff. This trust is essential, as it creates an environment where everyone feels empowered to contribute ideas and suggestions. Teachers, feeling valued and heard, are more motivated to actively participate in the school's safety programs, further strengthening the sense of teamwork and collaboration. In the long run, this unified approach makes the school a more resilient and well-prepared community, capable of effectively handling emergencies. According to Johnson and Lee (2019), fostering collaboration among school staff through regular safety drills and transparent communication is essential for creating a shared responsibility toward school safety. When school leaders encourage collaboration and ensure that all staff members are aware of safety protocols, it not only improves emergency preparedness but also

enhances the overall school climate by promoting trust and cooperation among educators and administrators.

3.1.4. Facing Limited Resources and Infrastructure —In many public schools, the absence of functional equipment, insufficient security personnel, or outdated facilities limits the full implementation of safety measures, placing added burden on teachers. Many public schools continue to struggle with a limited adequate resources and infrastructure, which severely limits the implementation of effective safety and security measures. In some cases, essential equipment such as fire extinguishers, alarm systems, first-aid kits, and surveillance cameras are either outdated or completely absent. This creates a vulnerable environment not only for students but also for teachers who are often expected to manage emergency situations with little to no support. Without the necessary tools and physical infrastructure, even the best-planned safety protocols become difficult to enforce consistently. Moreover, the shortage of trained security personnel and emergency support staff forces teachers to take on responsibilities beyond their primary role as educators. This added burden causes stress and distracts them from their instructional duties. Teachers are often left to monitor entry points, supervise drills, or respond to emergencies without sufficient training or backup. These limitations not only compromise the overall safety of the school but also impact the morale and confidence of teachers, who may feel unprepared or unsupported in crisis situations. Ramos and Cruz (2020) assert that the implementation of school safety initiatives is severely hampered by public schools' inadequate infrastructure and safety resources, particularly in impoverished and rural locations. They stress that even though policies may exist, teachers bear a disproportionate amount of the load. Teachers are expected to create a safe atmosphere with few resources and institutional assistance. The interview reveals the daily chal-

lenges teachers face due to the lack of resources and infrastructure in many schools. The absence of essential safety equipment—such as functioning fire extinguishers, emergency kits, and visible safety signs leaves teachers feeling unprepared to deal with potential emergencies. These small but critical elements are often overlooked, yet they are vital in ensuring timely and effective responses during crises. Without them, even well-planned safety drills lose their effectiveness, as the tools needed to execute them properly are missing. In addition, the responsibility for safety is falling heavily on the shoulders of teachers. The shortage of security personnel forces educators to perform tasks that are outside their professional training, such as gatekeeping and visitor monitoring. This adds a layer of stress to their already demanding roles as classroom managers and caregivers. Although teachers do their best to adapt by improvising solutions and working together the lack of institutional support is both physically and emotionally draining. It highlights a broader systemic issue: while teachers are committed to protecting students, they need adequate tools and infrastructure to fulfill that responsibility effectively. Research shows that inadequate safety infrastructure in schools negatively affects both teacher performance and student well-being. A study by Dela Cruz and Santos (2021) found that many public schools in the Philippines lack basic emergency tools, with only 45% equipped with complete fire and earthquake preparedness kits. The study further explains that this shortage not only compromises safety but also forces teachers to assume roles that detract from their instructional duties, increasing stress and reducing teaching effectiveness. Similarly, Navarro and Lim (2019) argue that safety cannot rely solely on human initiative when structural and logistical support is lacking. Their findings emphasize that while teachers are willing to take on added responsibilities during emergencies, expecting them to compensate for system-level

shortcomings is unsustainable. Providing sufficient security staff, updated facilities, and accessible safety tools is critical for establishing a truly safe and supportive learning environment.

3.2. Increasing Workload and Stress— Teachers often experience increased stress due to the responsibility of enforcing safety protocols, conducting drills, and managing large groups during emergencies, on top of their teaching duties. Teachers face significant added workload and stress due to their expanded roles in enforcing safety measures within schools. Beyond lesson planning and classroom instruction, they are tasked with organizing and leading safety drills, managing large groups of students during emergencies, and ensuring that safety protocols are followed daily. These responsibilities require extra time, emotional energy, and focus—resources already stretched thin by their core teaching duties. This dual role not only increases physical fatigue but also contributes to mental strain, as the pressure to protect students in high-stakes situations adds to their sense of accountability. According to Martinez and Ramos (2020), the growing demand for teachers to take on safety-related responsibilities without additional support or training contributes to heightened levels of job stress and burnout. Their study found that many educators feel overwhelmed by the expectation to act as both instructors and safety officers, especially during emergencies where quick decision-making is critical. They recommend systemic changes, including designated safety personnel and institutional backing, to relieve teachers from having to bear these burdens alone. Figure 3 illustrates the experiences of teachers regarding current safety and security measures in schools, categorizing them into two major themes: positive experiences and challenges. On the positive side, teachers reported enhanced preparedness and confidence during emergencies, attributing this to regular drills and clear protocols that have trained them to respond

Fig. 3. Experiences of the Teachers in the Current School Safety and Security Measures

more effectively. This preparedness boosts their confidence in managing students safely during critical situations, such as earthquakes or fire drills. Additionally, it helps instill calmness and readiness among learners, contributing to a safer school environment. Another significant positive experience is the improved sense of security among staff and students. The presence of security guards, surveillance cameras, and updated visitor policies has increased the perception of safety. Teachers and students feel more at ease knowing that physical and procedural barriers are in place to prevent threats. Along-

side this is the theme of stronger collaboration and awareness, where teamwork has become more prominent in handling safety measures. Despite these gains, teachers still face serious challenges. Chief among them is the limited resources and infrastructure, such as inadequate emergency kits, outdated fire extinguishers, and surveillance cameras. These gaps place more pressure on teachers, who must often improvise safety solutions. Furthermore, they also experience added workload and stress due to these responsibilities and without additional support or compensation.

3.3. *Overcoming the Challenges in the Implementation of Safety and Security measures in the school*—The implementation of safety and security measures in schools is a fundamental aspect of creating a nurturing and secure learning environment for students. Teachers, as the primary caregivers and facilitators of education, play a critical role in ensuring that these

measures are effectively carried out. However, various challenges arise in the process, such as inadequate resources, lack of training, and insufficient collaboration between school staff, parents, and local authorities. Teachers are often at the forefront of managing emergency situations, addressing students’ safety concerns, and maintaining an atmosphere where both phys-

ical and emotional well-being are prioritized. These challenges not only require immediate attention but also long-term strategies to ensure that safety measures are sustained. Overcoming these obstacles involves a combination of proactive planning, professional development, and the development of a school-wide culture focused on security and preparedness. Teachers must navigate through various complexities, including balancing the demands of daily teaching

3.3.1. Collaborating and Communicating—Teachers work closely with school administrators, security staff, parents, and local law enforcement to create a cohesive safety plan. Open lines of communication ensure that everyone is aware of their roles and responsibilities in maintaining a safe environment. Regular meetings, drills, and updates help teachers stay informed about potential threats or changes in security protocols. By fostering strong partnerships, teachers can effectively respond to emerging safety concerns and create a unified front in addressing security issues. Collaboration and communication among teachers, school administrators, security personnel, parents, and local law enforcement are essential for the effective implementation of safety and security measures in schools. Teachers need to be well-informed about the roles and responsibilities of all stakeholders to ensure that everyone works towards a common goal of maintaining a safe environment. Regular meetings and updates between these parties help teachers stay aware of new threats, policy changes, and best practices for handling various safety concerns. In addition, safety drills, such as fire drills and lockdown procedures, ensure that both teachers and students are prepared to respond quickly and appropriately in case of an emergency. By creating a collaborative atmosphere, teachers can strengthen the school's overall safety framework and ensure that safety

with the need to stay vigilant to safety concerns. Collaboration with administrators, security personnel, and local law enforcement, along with engaging students in awareness programs, can strengthen the school's security protocols. By addressing these challenges, teachers contribute significantly to fostering a secure and positive learning environment that allows students to thrive academically and personally.

protocols are implemented effectively. Moreover, fostering strong communication networks helps to address any emerging security issues promptly. Teachers are often the first line of defense when it comes to identifying potential risks within the school. With an established line of communication, teachers can quickly report concerns to administrators, who can then work with security staff and law enforcement to address the situation. Effective collaboration between school staff and parents is also crucial, as it allows for the sharing of valuable information regarding students' emotional or behavioral well-being, which can impact school safety. Ultimately, by maintaining strong partnerships and open communication, schools can create a proactive and responsive approach to security, ensuring the well-being of both students and staff (National School Safety Center, 2019). Effective collaboration is crucial in establishing a cohesive and responsive safety plan in schools. According to IDI 6, teachers consistently engage in regular meetings with school administrators, security personnel, and even local law enforcement to discuss current safety protocols and emerging threats. These collaborative sessions foster mutual understanding and ensure that all stakeholders are aligned in their safety responsibilities. By involving various sectors of the school community, a comprehensive and well-rounded approach to safety can be developed, allowing for a more effective im-

plementation of preventive and responsive measures. Clear communication is a foundational component of successful safety planning. As highlighted in IDI 7, these meetings not only serve as platforms for planning but also ensure that all participants fully understand their roles and responsibilities. Establishing well-defined communication channels enables swift and accurate dissemination of information, especially during emergencies. Teachers recognize that misunderstandings or lapses in communication can lead to confusion, delays, or even heightened risk during crisis situations, making clarity

and consistency in messaging a top priority. Furthermore, regular safety drills play a vital role in reinforcing preparedness. As shared in FGD 6 and 8, schools conduct routine exercises such as fire drills and lockdown simulations to familiarize both staff and students with the appropriate actions to take during emergencies. These drills help identify potential gaps in the system and ensure that the entire school community can respond effectively and efficiently. Practicing these protocols fosters confidence and reduces panic, making the school better equipped to handle real-life emergencies.

3.3.2. Developing Professionally and Training —To effectively manage safety and security in schools, teachers must receive ongoing training in areas such as emergency response procedures, conflict resolution, and recognizing warning signs of potential threats. This professional development equips teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to act swiftly and confidently in crisis situations. Teachers who are well-trained in safety protocols are better prepared to prevent accidents and respond appropriately to emergencies, thus ensuring a safer learning environment for all. Professional development and training are essential components in equipping teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively implement school safety and security measures. Teachers are often the first responders during emergencies, and without proper training, their ability to manage crises may be limited. Through regular workshops, seminars, and simulation exercises, teachers learn how to handle various situations such as natural disasters, lockdowns, medical emergencies, and behavioral threats. These training sessions also emphasize early detection of warning signs related to bullying, mental health issues, and potential violence, allowing teachers to intervene proactively and prevent escalation. Moreover, ongoing pro-

fessional development ensures that teachers stay updated with the latest safety protocols, legal responsibilities, and best practices in crisis management. As school safety concerns evolve, so too must the preparedness of educators. Training also builds teachers' confidence and fosters a culture of shared responsibility within the school community. When all staff members are well-informed and prepared, they can collaborate more effectively and respond more efficiently during emergencies. As argued by Cornell (2019), investing in professional development for school safety enhances not only emergency preparedness but also contributes to a more supportive and secure learning environment for all students. Professional development and training have become essential strategies for schools in preparing teachers to respond effectively to emergencies and uphold a safe learning environment. As highlighted by participant P6, recent seminars and workshops focused on school emergency protocols were highly informative and practical, particularly because of the inclusion of hands-on simulations. These experiential learning opportunities allow teachers to apply safety protocols in simulated scenarios, which enhances their preparedness for real-life situations. Such simulations bridge the gap between theory and practice, helping

educators internalize procedures more effectively. Participant P7 emphasized how these trainings have improved their confidence and clarity in responding to emergencies. Initially feeling uncertain during safety drills, the teacher noted a significant shift in preparedness after attending professional development sessions. This transition from uncertainty to confidence highlights the importance of not just having safety plans, but ensuring that staff are mentally and practically equipped to implement them. Comprehensive training empowers teachers to act decisively and reduce potential harm during critical incidents. The frequency and timing of these training sessions were also mentioned as

key factors in their effectiveness. According to P8, most trainings are held at the beginning of the school year and occasionally at midyear, depending on updates from the Department of Education or local government units. While these schedules ensure that safety measures are introduced or refreshed annually, P9 raised a valid concern about the need for more frequent refresher courses. With the constant evolution of school safety threats—such as cybersecurity issues, climate-related hazards, and mental health crises—teachers must continually update their skills and knowledge to remain responsive to emerging challenges.

3.3.3. Creating a Positive School Culture— Promoting a culture of respect, inclusion, and awareness is essential in preventing safety issues. Teachers play a key role in fostering positive relationships among students, promoting empathy, and teaching conflict resolution skills. By addressing bullying, promoting mental health awareness, and encouraging respectful behavior, teachers can create a supportive atmosphere that reduces the likelihood of security concerns. When students feel valued and respected, they are more likely to engage in positive behavior, contributing to a safer school environment overall. The safety, wellbeing, and academic achievement of students are all dependent on the establishment of a strong school culture. Students and staff feel a sense of belonging in a school setting that values mutual support, respect, and inclusivity. Positive behavior and active learning are more likely to be displayed by students who feel appreciated and connected. Similar to this, educators who work in schools with a positive culture feel inspired and encouraged, which enhances their efficiency in the classroom and helps them advance professionally. By lowering the possibility of disputes and behavioral problems, this type of setting im-

proves general safety. A noted strategy of fostering a positive school culture is the implementation of value-based programming and well-defined behavior expectations. Schools that set expectations alongside consistent communication and celebration of student successes foster a trusting and collaborative school climate. Teachers model respect and emotional safety, which forms the basis of their relationships with students. When students perceive their teachers as nurturing with firm expectations, it enhances the likelihood of developing prosocial behaviors and resilience. Recognition and positive regard also contribute to the building of a culture that champions caring and responsibility. Moreover, collaborative efforts among teachers, school leaders, parents, and students are essential in sustaining a healthy school culture. Regular dialogue, shared decision-making, and inclusive school events promote strong relationships and a sense of shared responsibility. O'Connor et al. (2019) claim that schools that make investments in relational trust and collective teacher efficacy have greater success executing school improvement programs and preserving a secure and encouraging learning environment. The entire school community must be committed to

and actively involved in the ongoing process of developing a positive school culture. Creating a positive school culture is a collaborative and ongoing process that deeply impacts both student well-being and academic success. As shared by IDI 1, a warm and welcoming atmosphere is fostered by prioritizing respect, kindness, and collaboration among teachers, students, and staff. When school stakeholders work together to build trust and maintain positive interactions, it cultivates a sense of community and belonging. This supportive environment not only makes students feel safe but also empowers them to participate more actively in their learning and social development. One key approach school use to promote positive behavior is the implementation of values-based programs. According to IDI 2, their school highlights one core value each month—such as honesty, empathy, or responsibility which helps set a tone for

behavior across the school community. These values are not just discussed in theory; as IDI 4 explains, teachers integrate them into their daily lessons, and students who demonstrate these values are recognized. This regular reinforcement helps students internalize important life principles and encourages them to act accordingly, both inside and outside the classroom. Creating emotionally safe spaces is also a vital part of fostering a positive school culture. As FGD 5 mentions, teachers actively listen to students, encourage self-expression, and respond with empathy when students face personal or academic challenges. This practice not only builds students' confidence but also strengthens the student-teacher relationship. When students feel heard and valued, they are more likely to respect others and take ownership of their actions.

3.4. Educational Management Insights — The topic "Navigating School Safety and Security: Teachers' Lived Experiences" provides valuable insights into the day-to-day challenges and strategies teachers employ to ensure a secure learning environment. Teachers, as the front-line responders in managing school safety, share firsthand accounts of how they address various security concerns, from routine safety drills to crisis situations. Their lived experi-

ences reveal the complexities of balancing educational goals with maintaining a safe space for students. By understanding these perspectives, educational management can identify effective practices, foster a culture of collaboration, and implement continuous professional development to enhance overall school security. The findings from this study offer crucial lessons for school leaders, policymakers, and educators in creating resilient, supportive, and secure educational settings.

3.4.1. Ensuring School Safety Through Collaborative Leadership — One significant insight is that school safety and security require collaborative leadership among school heads, teachers, support staff, parents, and even local authorities. Participants consistently emphasized the effectiveness of regular communication, joint planning, and shared decision-

making in creating a safer school environment. Educational leaders must facilitate partnerships, organize regular safety drills, and maintain open lines of communication. This collective effort builds trust and allows for a more proactive and coordinated response to potential threats. A key insight into ensuring school safety is the importance of collaborative leadership, where

Fig. 4. Overcoming the Challenges in the Implementation of Safety and Security measures in the school

school heads, teachers, support staff, parents, and local authorities work together to establish and maintain a safe environment. Teachers and school leaders emphasized the need for constant communication and collaboration in planning and executing safety measures. Regular meetings between administrators, teachers, and external partners, such as local law enforcement, allow everyone to stay informed about potential risks and update protocols accordingly. This approach fosters a shared responsibility for school safety, ensuring that all parties are aware of their roles and ready to respond effectively during emergencies. By creating a cohesive leadership team, schools can navigate safety challenges more efficiently and ensure that their plans are adaptable and comprehensive. Moreover, joint decision-making and input from various stakeholders promote a sense of ownership and trust within the school community. When teachers, parents, and other staff members are involved in safety initiatives, it strengthens their commitment to following protocols and supporting each other during crises. Collaborative leadership also enables a more proactive stance on safety, as it encourages the identification of risks before they escalate into serious problems. Regular safety drills and simulations, coordinated through teamwork, allow staff to practice their roles in a controlled environment, ensuring that they are better prepared to act swiftly and decisively in the event of a real emergency (O'Connor et al., 2019). In the context of school safety, the approach taken by the school highlights the importance of a collaborative effort among all members of the school community. The idea of working together, rather than leaving safety responsibilities solely to administrators or security staff, ensures that everyone—teachers, staff, and even parents—are well aware of their roles in an emergency. This shared responsibility creates a unified approach to safety, allowing for a more efficient response when challenges arise. The school is better equipped to manage emergencies when everyone is aware of their unique responsibilities and has a well-coordinated strategy (Alivernini et al., 2019). The involvement of parents further strengthens the safety framework by fostering greater community engagement. When parents are informed about safety drills and actively participate in school events, they gain a deeper understanding of the importance of these measures. Their awareness extends beyond the school gates, as they can assist in reinforcing safety principles at home and with their children. Additionally, parents provide valuable feedback on any concerns their children may have, ensuring that the school is responsive to potential safety issues that may not be immediately apparent to teachers and administrators (O'Connor et al., 2019). Moreover, collaboration with local authorities plays a crucial role in preparing for potential external threats. By engaging with law enforcement and other community agencies, schools can enhance their preparedness for crises that may arise beyond the school's immediate control. This partnership allows for better coordination during emergencies, such as natural disasters or security threats, and ensures that the school can act swiftly and decisively when needed. Having external partners involved also builds trust and a sense of collective responsibility, making it easier for all parties to respond effectively to crises (Alivernini et al., 2019). Lastly, the practice of regular joint planning and safety drills strengthens the overall school safety culture. Teachers, parents, and students all play an active role in these activities, ensuring that everyone is familiar with emergency protocols. The involvement of all stakeholders in these drills enhances communication and allows for a seamless response when real situations occur. The ongoing communication and training not only prepare individuals for emergencies but also foster a culture of readiness and support within the school community (O'Connor et al., 2019).

3.4.2. Continuously Developing Professionally as a Key Strategy—Another key insight is the need for ongoing capacity-building and professional development in safety protocols and emergency response. Teachers expressed those seminars, workshops, and hands-on simulations greatly improved their preparedness and confidence in crisis situations. From an educational management perspective, school leaders should prioritize institutionalized safety training, provide periodic refreshers, and align practices with current policies. Investing in teachers' preparedness not only enhances safety but also promotes a culture of responsiveness and resilience within the school community. A crucial insight drawn from the experiences of teachers is the importance of continuous professional development (CPD) in ensuring preparedness for safety and emergency response. Teachers reported that seminars, workshops, and hands-on simulations significantly boosted their confidence and readiness to handle emergencies. These training opportunities not only provided teachers with the necessary skills but also helped them feel more equipped to make quick, effective decisions in crisis situations. The regular exposure to safety protocols through these professional development activities ensures that teachers remain updated on the latest practices and strategies for responding to emergencies, fostering a proactive mindset within the school. From an educational management standpoint, CPD is an essential strategy in maintaining high standards of school safety and crisis management. In addition, the role of institutionalized safety training is critical in building a school culture of responsiveness and resilience. Educational leaders must prioritize regular safety training, providing refresher courses to reinforce learned skills and ensure that teachers are aligned with current policies and practices. This commitment to ongoing professional development helps maintain a dynamic, well-prepared teaching force that can swiftly adapt

to changing safety challenges. In addition to improving immediate crisis response, schools may foster a culture of resilience in the face of adversity and continuous learning by consistently investing in the professional development of teachers in regard to safety (Alivernini et al., 2019). Based from the narratives, Over the past year, the school has invested in a series of seminars and workshops that focused specifically on emergency protocols, and this has significantly enhanced teachers' preparedness. The hands-on simulations during these sessions proved to be particularly valuable, as they gave teachers the opportunity to practice their roles in a real-life scenario. Unlike theoretical knowledge, these simulations allowed participants to immerse themselves in emergency situations, which helped to bridge the gap between knowledge and action. Teachers reported feeling more confident in their ability to respond quickly and effectively in an actual emergency situation (Alivernini et al., 2019). One of the key takeaways from the training sessions is the importance of active participation in safety drills and protocols. It is one thing to read about safety measures, but it is quite another to physically walk through them. Teachers shared that the practical aspect of the training gave them a better understanding of how to respond to emergencies, making them feel more prepared. This hands-on experience is crucial, as it ensures that teachers not only know what to do but also feel confident and calm when responding to emergencies, which ultimately benefits the entire school community. Furthermore, safety protocols and emergency response practices are continually evolving, and with the dynamic nature of the school environment, it is essential for teachers to stay updated. Teachers emphasized the need for frequent refresher courses to ensure they are always aligned with the latest safety guidelines and best practices. More frequent training sessions would help keep everyone sharp and ready for any situation, en-

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights

Ensuring that staff are equipped to handle both predictable and unexpected emergencies. These sessions also allow teachers to address any concerns, ask questions, and clarify any uncertainties they might have about their roles during an emergency. Finally, from an educational leadership perspective, it is vital that school leaders create an environment where safety training is embedded in the school culture. Teachers stressed that consistent and structured profes-

sional development should be a priority, fostering an atmosphere of readiness and resilience. By investing in continuous professional development, school leaders can build a responsive and prepared school community that can handle any crisis effectively. This ongoing commitment to safety and training ensures that both students and staff are well-equipped to respond to emergencies, making the school a safer place for everyone (Alivernini et al., 2019).

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter offers an integrated overview of the study’s findings on school safety and security, particularly focusing on the experiences of teachers. It outlines important implications and offers recommendations for addressing safety concerns while attending to the welfare of teachers. The study looked into the difficulties encountered by teachers in providing safety for pupils and themselves amidst the competing professional demands placed on them.

4.1. Findings—The findings highlight the necessity for comprehensive safety protocols, effective communication between school leadership and staff, and a collaborative approach to risk management. The study underscores

the importance of empowering teachers through training, resources, and a supportive school culture, which not only enhances safety but also fosters a sense of security and professional fulfillment. Additionally, the research advocates

for a proactive approach to school safety, with an emphasis on preventive measures, teacher involvement in safety planning, and creating a resilient, responsive school community.

4.2. Implications—The study reveals that teachers’ experiences in navigating school safety and security are significantly shaped by both the strength of safety measures in place and the degree of institutional support provided. When schools have clear, well-communicated safety protocols and resources, teachers report increased confidence during emergencies, enhanced collaboration, and a greater sense of security for both themselves and their students. These outcomes are notably reinforced by positive school culture and leadership that prioritize safety. This suggests that for teachers to thrive within a safe school environment, educational institutions must equally invest in both their physical and emotional well-being, alongside their instructional duties. Despite these positive developments, the challenges associated with safety and security remain significant. Teachers often face limitations in resources and infrastructure, which hinder their ability to effectively implement safety measures. Furthermore, the added workload and stress associated with safety protocols can overwhelm teachers, reducing their capacity to maintain a balanced approach to their professional roles. The lack of comprehensive safety support systems exacerbates these challenges, creating a sense of vulnerability among educators. This highlights the urgent need for systemic change, where schools not only acknowledge these issues but also develop actionable policies to mitigate them. Without such efforts, even the most dedicated teachers may struggle to maintain their professional focus and effectiveness. The study also underscores the resilience of teachers who navigate these safety challenges daily. Their unwavering commitment to ensuring a secure environment for their students, despite limited resources and high demands, reflects a deep sense of responsibility and emotional strength. However, relying solely on personal coping strategies is not a sustainable solution. This finding suggests that teacher resilience must be supported by structural mechanisms—such as ongoing professional development, access to resources, and adequate infrastructure—to ensure both teacher well-being and the effective management of school safety. From an educational management perspective, the findings emphasize the importance of collaborative leadership in fostering a culture that values safety. Schools must move beyond reactive approaches to safety and security and instead implement proactive, strategic policies. These policies should be consistently applied, well-defined, and tailored to address the specific needs of the teaching staff. By prioritizing teacher involvement in safety planning and providing the necessary tools and resources, schools not only enhance safety but also contribute to the overall well-being and effectiveness of the school community. The study also suggests that empowering teachers through professional autonomy and collaboration is a critical factor in navigating safety challenges. When teachers are entrusted with decision-making power and encouraged to collaborate with colleagues, they feel more supported and in control. This insight highlights the importance of participatory leadership practices that foster mutual respect, transparency, and shared responsibility. Prioritizing safety through open communication and teacher involvement is essential for creating a thriving, resilient, and secure educational environment. In order for teachers to attain greater levels of job satisfaction, professional engagement, and well-being, their basic needs for safety and security must be satisfied, according to Taormina and Gao’s (2023) modified version of Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs

(1943). Meeting these basic requirements is essential for teachers' own resilience as well as their capacity to support a secure, productive learning environment. In order to ensure that teachers feel empowered, appreciated, and sup-

ported in their duties, educational management must take these demands into account when creating measures to improve safety and security in schools.

4.3. Future Directions—In light of the study's conclusions, it is critical that important stakeholders actively take into account and use the knowledge acquired to improve school safety and security, guaranteeing both the well-being of teachers and the security of students in learning environments.

Teachers

Teachers themselves can gain from enhanced understanding of their functions in the fostering of school safety, as well as the necessity to take care of their own safety and wellness. Essential self-care and peer support, along with set boundaries, should be embraced while attending to the multifaceted demands of school safety. This involves acknowledging personal limits and utilizing available resources, such as professional development programs, to improve their skills in handling security measures. By prioritizing their well-being, teachers will be better equipped to manage safety concerns, thereby enhancing their effectiveness and contributing to a safer and more supportive school environment.

Students

Students equally contribute towards maintaining a healthy and secure school environment. Their knowledge of safety measures, active engagement during practice drills, as well as working along with the teaching staff, contributes immensely to the security of the school. Students should be encouraged to voice their concerns, engage in peer support, and practice respect for school safety measures. When students are empowered to contribute to the safety culture, they help foster a community where everyone feels secure and valued.

School Principals/School Heads

Addressing safety issues proactively ensures that a school is both supportive and protective. The challenges appointed to a school's safety measures, whether they stem from inadequate resources, insufficient training, or overwhelming teacher workloads, should always be attended to by principals. Safety protocols that must as workable as and not overbearing for teachers need to be enacted. Professional development has to be provided and teachers have to be able to voice concerns safely without fear of being penalized. There should be commended triadic collaboration within the school and communication all around. School leaders bolster a school's safety by ensuring, and that reinforce teachers are supported in their safety efforts and ensured that they are able to meet security challenges.

Department of Education

This study's findings may assist the Department of Education in developing policies that balance security with teacher welfare. Given the difficulties teachers encounter with maintaining school safety alongside their duties, the department may want to devise plans that combine safety protocols with wellness program frameworks. These frameworks could include clear guidelines on resource allocation for safety measures, mental health support for educators, and professional development focused on navigating safety concerns effectively. By prioritizing both safety and teacher wellness, the department can contribute to creating safer school environments that also promote job satisfaction, teacher retention, and improved student outcomes.

Other Stakeholders

Support for school safety programs is also crucial from parents, neighbors, and local partners. They may help by recognizing the significance of school safety and supporting laws and initiatives that assist educators in their capacity as safety supervisors. Offering safety drill materials, starting safety campaigns, or assisting schools in setting up areas where instructors may gather and exchange experiences on security issues are a few examples of community involvement. These stakeholders can contribute to the development of a more cooperative and encouraging atmosphere for teachers by acknowledging the connection between teacher well-being and school safety, which will ultimately benefit the entire school community.

Future Researchers

Forthcoming studies could examine the influence of safety training on teachers' perceived security, the urban-rural divide challenges in educational institutions, and the contribution of school administration towards fostering secure spaces within schools. Furthermore, research could analyze the intersection of teacher wellness and school safety by exploring the psychologically and emotionally protective impacts, or lack thereof, reserving safety protocols for teachers. Incorporating the views of school administration, students, and parents would broaden the understanding of the intricacies of school safety and security.

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